

oxalate, UO_2^{II} in case of Pd^{II} and tartrate and thiocyanate in case of Ni^{II} do not interfere in the estimations. Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mg^{II} , Tl^I , Cd^{II} , Rh^{III} , Pt^{IV} and Mo^{VI} do not interfere with the determinations of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} . Metal ions such as Pd^{II} , V^V , Ti^{IV} , Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , Sn^{II} , Ru^{III} , Bi^{III} and Re^{VII} interfere in the estimation of both the metal ions.

Determination of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} by separation from their binary mixture: To an aliquot of an acidic mixture of both the metal ions taken in a separatory funnel was added 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution (3.0 ml) and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.1 by adding requisite amount of 0.1 N HCl in a total volume of 20 ml made up with double-distilled water. The Pd^{II} complex was then quantitatively extracted in CHCl_3 , the extraction being made thrice by adding small portions of chloroform at a time. The absorbances of the solutions after drying over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 were measured at 560 nm against the reagent blank. The aqueous layer remaining after the extraction of Pd^{II} complex was treated with 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution (3.0 ml) and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 7–9 adding ammonium-acetate–ammonia buffer in a final volume of 25 ml. The absorbances of aqueous alcoholic solution of the Ni^{II} complex was then measured at 485 nm against the appropriate reagent blank. Results are stated in Table I.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF Pd^{II} AND Ni^{II} FROM THEIR BINARY MIXTURE

Metal ions ppm	Pd^{II} found ppm	Ni^{II} found ppm
3.00 Pd^{II}	2.98	—
3.00 Ni^{II}	—	3.01
1.00 Pd^{II}	0.99	—
4.00 Ni^{II}	—	4.02
2.00 Pd^{II}	2.02	—
6.00 Ni^{II}	—	5.98

Precision and accuracy: 3 ppm of metal in both the cases in 10 determinations was used for finding standard deviations, the values being $\pm 0.18\%$ for Ni^{II} and $\pm 0.46\%$ for Pd^{II} estimations, respectively.

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Trace Determination of Terbium(III), Dysprosium(III) and Erbium(III) using 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol as an Amperometric Reagent

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4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (abbreviated as PAR) has been widely used for the trace determination^{1–3} of various transition metal ions. Its use as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of rare earths has also been discussed in the literature^{4–6}. The spectrophotometric method can not be used when precipitation occurs, nor it can be applied at the close proximity of the wavelength of absorption of complex and the ligand. PAR has been successfully used as an amperometric reagent for the trace determination of some rare earths^{7,8}, in our laboratory. In continuation to our work, the results of amperometric titration of Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} and Er^{III} with PAR have been reported in this paper. The metal–ligand stoichiometry has been supplemented by spectral analysis.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Solutions of Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} and Er^{III} were prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of the metal oxide/nitrate of each metal in minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid and making up the solution to

the required volume with distilled water and standardised⁹. The PAR (E. Merck) solution was prepared by dissolving monosodium salt of the reagent and was standardized potentiometrically¹⁰. A manually operated polarograph with multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.0×10^{-9} A/div.) was used for the purpose of amperometric titrations. A d.m.e. mercury-pool electrode system was used for the studies. The capillary used for d.m.e. had a m value 2.3712 mg s^{-1} at a drop time of 3.0 s in air-free 1 M KCl solution at 25 cm effective height of mercury column ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$). The pH of the test solution was adjusted to 6.1 ± 0.02 using dilute HCl/NaOH solutions. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

The current-voltage relationship for PAR was studied in 0.5 M KCl at $\text{pH} 6.1 \pm 0.02$. PAR gave a well defined polarographic reduction wave Fig. 1 (A). It's polarogram at different concentrations were recorded and it was observed that the diffusion current is proportional to the PAR concentration.

Fig. 1. (A) Polarogram of 1 mM PAR in 0.5 M KCl at $\text{pH}=6.1$, (B) Polarogram of 2 mM metal (Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} or Er^{III}) in 0.5 M KCl at $\text{pH}=6.1$.

For amperometric titrations, sets of solution containing a known amount of each of the titled metal ions in 0.5 M KCl in 10 ml volume were prepared. The pH of each set was adjusted to 6.1 ± 0.02 . The metal solution was taken in titration cell. The plateau potential for the PAR wave, i.e. 0.85 V vs Hg pool was applied. Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} and Er^{III} do not produce a polarographic wave at this potential. The current was noted on a galvanometer. Standard solution of PAR ($\text{pH} 6.1 \pm 0.02$) was added drop by drop to the test solution from a semi-micro burette (1 cm³). The current was noted after each addition of the titrant. The plot of galvanometer deflection after necessary volume correction was made against the volume of PAR added and yielded a reversed L-shaped curve in each case (Fig. 2). The L-shaped curves may

Fig. 2. Amperometric titration curves of (a) 0.005 mM/10 ml PAR with 0.005 mM/ml Tb^{III} , (b) 0.002 mM/10 ml PAR with 0.001 mM/ml Dy^{III} and (c) 0.004 mM/10 ml PAR with 0.002 mM/ml Dy^{III} .

be obtained by choosing PAR as titrate and metal as titrant under identical experimental conditions. The end-point indicated a metal to PAR ratio of 1 : 2.

Interference studies : For the study of the effect of diverse ions on the titration procedure, known amounts of foreign ions, viz. alkali and alkaline earth metal ions (10 mg), ammoinum (10 mg), Tl^{I} (10 mg), Cr^{III} (12 mg), molybdate (12 mg), chloride (15 mg), chlorate (10 mg), nitrate (15 mg), sulphate (12 mg), acetate (10 mg) etc. were added to the titrate and the titrations performed. It was observed that the titrations were not hampered by the presence of the above mentioned ions. However, the presence of a small amount of Cd^{II} , Bi^{III} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , phosphate, carbonate etc. interferred the titration procedure seriously.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 represents the results of amperometric titrations of the titled metal ions. The minimum amount (~ 0.16 mg) of each of the said metal ions could be determined successfully with a practical error of less than $\pm 0.75\%$. The standard deviation is 0.21% and the coefficient of variance never exceeded 0.52. The minimum detection limit of PAR is nearly five times to that observed with cupferron, ARS and xylene orange. The study on these reagents as amperometric reagents has been done earlier in our laboratory. The above experimental data and calculated statistical values confirm the accuracy and precision of the discussed amperometric titration method.

Study of metal-ligand complexation equilibrium : The visible absorption spectra of 0.05 mM PAR at $\text{pH} 6.1$ consists of a single maximum at 450 nm. In

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF Tb^{III}, Dy^{III} AND Er^{III} WITH PAR
 Plateau potential = -0.85 V vs S.C.E., $\mu=0.5$, pH=6.1 $\pm$ 0.02

Sl. no.	Approx concn.	Amounts of Tb ^{III}			Error %	Amounts of Dy ^{III}			Error %	Amounts of Er ^{III}		
		Taken mg	Found mg			Taken mg	Found mg			Taken mg	Found mg	
1.	1 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.158 0	0.152 2	+0.75	0.162 5	0.161 2	-0.80	0.167 2	0.168 4	+0.71		
2.	2 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.316 0	0.318 4	+0.75	0.325 0	0.326 8	+0.55	0.334 5	0.337 2	+0.80		
3.	4 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.632 0	0.629 6	-0.37	0.650 0	0.652 8	+0.43	0.669 0	0.664 8	-0.62		
4.	6 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.948 0	0.945 2	-0.29	0.975 0	0.971 2	-0.39	1.003 6	1.000 8	-0.27		
5.	8 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	1.264 0	1.267 6	+0.28	1.300 0	1.303 6	+0.27	1.338 0	1.339 8	-0.13		
6.	1 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	1.580 0	1.574 8	-0.32	1.625 0	1.621 0	-0.24	1.672 6	1.681 2	+0.51		
7.	1.5 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	2.370 0	2.377 0	+0.29	2.437 4	2.446 6	+0.37	2.508 8	2.518 4	+0.38		
8.	2 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	3.160 0	3.169 0	+0.28	3.250 0	3.238 0	-0.36	3.345 2	3.328 4	-0.50		
9.	2.5 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	3.950 0	3.963 0	+0.33	4.062 5	4.079 2	+0.41	4.181 5	4.162 0	-0.46		
10.	3 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	4.740 0	4.723 0	-0.35	4.875 0	4.860 6	-0.29	5.017 8	5.003 4	-0.28		

the presence of rare earth ions Tb^{III}, Dy^{III} and Er^{III}, $\lambda_{\max}$ of PAR shifted to 505 nm due to complex formation. Study of the composition of these complexes by Job's method¹¹ of continuous variation revealed the formation of 1:2 metal-ligand complex with each of the Tb^{III}, Dy^{III} and Er^{III} with PAR, which was in agreement with the observation of the amperometric titrations. The log overall conditional formation constants of the 1:2 rare-earth-PAR complexes were evaluated by mole-ratio method and non-linear method of Job, and were found to be 6.96, 7.35 and 7.81 for Tb^{III}, Dy^{III} and Er^{III} complexes, respectively.

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